

Chikankari Embroidery - The Beauty of Intricacy

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Abstract:

The handicraft industry is a crucial player in the economy, creating jobs, enhancing productivity, and stimulating socio-economic development, particularly in rural and semi-urban areas. Among its various forms, Chikankari embroidery remains a profound artistic cultural tradition. It is believed that Chikankari was introduced by Empress Noor Jahan wife of Emperor Jahangir in India's royal courts where it was so much loved for its intricate beauty. Over centuries this embroidery changed from being a symbol of social status to an intricate art form tied to culture and adaptability.

This paper examines the origins and historical development of Chikankari its traditional techniques and the processes involved in producing it. The study sets out to trace its journey from being a royal pastime to becoming part of modern fashion trends, thereby illuminating how Chikankari is an art that endures. The retention and adaptation of traditional techniques within modern-day fashion designs or cultural identities are underscored. Additionally, the article analyses tools and techniques used in making up Chikankari pieces, their transformation over time, and the effects of contemporary marketing approaches on the global acceptance of this craft.

Keywords: *adaptability, Chikankari, Lucknawi Embroidery, Needlecraft, White on white work*

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1. Introduction

Handicrafts play a vital role in the cultural and economic tapestry of the world at large. Artisanal crafts represent not only the identity, traditions, and heritage of a community, but also the values and practices it imbibes through the wheel of centuries-old crafts passed down from one generation to another. Handicrafts therefore, preserve cultural knowledge. They play an important role to maintain the local economies especially in the rural and poor regions, where it can be a source for livelihood, providing employment and social inclusion. Additionally, with a growing demand for authentic handmade products globally, handicrafts have made a bigger niche for itself in the international market where consumers look forward to experiencing the authenticity of tradition [1, 2]. As such, handicrafts represent both cultural wealth and a central engine of sustainable development [3]. One of the most popular handicrafts of India is embroidery, which involves decorating fabric with intricate patterns, motifs, and designs. There are many varieties of embroidery, and the type of fabric to be used is decided based on the design in mind and the texture and durability required [4]. Among these various embroidery techniques, Chikankari stands out as one of the most distinguished and respected techniques, tied deeply to the cultural identity of Lucknow. Known for its delicacy and sophistication, Chikankari is a hand-embroidered art form traditionally executed on muslin fabric, characterized by fine white thread work that forms elaborate floral and geometric patterns [5]. The roots of Chikankari are very closely related to the Mughal era, when it was perfected under the patronage of the Mughal Empress Noor Jahan, the wife of Emperor Jahangir. She played a pivotal role in popularizing this intricate needlework, making it a symbol of royal elegance and sophistication. This craft was first originated in Persia but was later taken to India during the Mughal period. It became popular in the royal courts, especially in the city of Lucknow. During the Nawabs of Awadh, Chikankari was one of the features that described the textile tradition of the region and was very often used in the elite courtly dress [6]. Chikankari embroidery is actually the subtlety and

refinement of the art. The soft, white cotton threads on a fine muslin produce an ethereal look, often coined as "shadow work" for its delicate, translucent effect. Floral motifs are common designs with intricate stems, leaves, and trailing vines, which evoke movement and grace in each of their etchings. This artistry is not just a form of aesthetic expression but has been passed down for generations, from mothers to daughters, as an inheritance to pass on skill and tradition within the family [7]. The craft of Chikankari gained widespread recognition when it was granted Geographical Indication (G.I.) status in 2008, recognizing its authentic and heritage-driven origin. This prestigious title protects the traditional craft from imitation and assures consumers of its cultural and artisanal authenticity [8]. The history of Chikankari is closely linked with the stories of patronage and cultural exchange, with the most popular one being with the Mughal Empress Noor Jahan, who is considered the pivotal influence behind the refinement of the craft in fashion and textile decoration. Accounts of Chikankari have it that the craft was related to fine muslins of high value among the royalty, making it a symbol of luxury and refinement [9].

Over time, Chikankari spread beyond the royal courts and became an integral part of local culture. Skilled artisans in Lucknow continued to produce exquisite pieces. The patterns and techniques of Chikankari were initially influenced by Mughal aesthetics, but over the centuries, the craft has evolved to incorporate regional variations. [10]. The rich history of the craft is reflected not only in its design but also in the stories behind it, such as the tale of a princess from Murshidabad, whose embroidered head covering, created as a token of love, inspired the tradition of Chikankari in the Nawabi courts of Lucknow [11]. Such anecdotes, though part of the legend, emphasize the emotional and cultural significance embedded in Chikankari embroidery. The long-lasting legacy of Chikankari speaks volumes about the cultural exchange between India and Persia, and how Mughal patronage impacted Indian arts and crafts [12]. Not only is the craft aesthetically pleasing, but it continues to provide economic opportunities for artisans in the region, particularly women, who have been the custodians of this art form for centuries. Chikankari is a part of India's intangible cultural heritage that continues to hold significant importance and has been appreciated for its craftsmanship, history, and the beauty it brings to textiles [13].

Figure 1 - Chikankari Carrie buti pattern, Neck Pattern, Sleeve pattern (Source: Authors Own)

2. Objectives

- To investigate the historical roots and evolution of Chikankari embroidery.
- To examine how Chikankari evolved from a royal diversion to a contemporary artistic and cultural legacy.
- To look into how historic methods are being used and adapted in modern fashion designs.
- To investigate the instruments and processes utilized in the creation of Chikankari and how they have changed throughout time.

3. Literature Review

3.1 Product and Material Diversification

To adapt to modern tastes, chikankari has now moved beyond cotton. Vibrant color combinations have been used, and experiments with textile materials like georgettes, chiffons, silks, modal, viscose, organza, and chanderi have been conducted [9].

Figure 2 - Chikankari Saree, Tunic, Anarkali, Sharara Pant, Trouser, Straight Pant (Source: Authors Own)

3.1(a) Techniques of Chikankari

Figure 3 - Making of Stamp (Chapai Buta for Chikankari) Source: Authors Own

Men predominate in every stage of production, except embroidery, where the majority of artisans are Muslim women [9]. Washable color and design-engraved wooden blocks are used to trace chikankari motifs onto fabric before they are embroidered. Before the cloth is mounted on smaller frames, stamping is done to print the designs using neel or dye. Traced patterns are stitched with a variety of standard stitches, including raised stitches like french knots and burion, as well as ordinary stitches like satin, back, stem, buttonhole, and chain. The designs are made with untwisted polyester and cotton threads in vivid colors and white. The type of thread that is utilized to make a segment that resembles mesh determines the pattern. Following completion of the Chikan process, the cloth is further bleached, acid-treated, and cleaned to eliminate the traced pattern and add rigidity. The completed piece is finally carefully ironed to improve its appearance [4].

Table 1 - Tools and Materials Used

Sr. No.	Tools and Materials used
1	Cotton fabric or Muslin or Silk Fabric
2	Wooden blocks or Stamp
3	Indigo color
4	Frame/ Adda
5	Needle
6	Thread cutter
7	Zari work (Optional)
6	Thread cutter
7	Zari work (Optional)

Figure 4 - Dhobi Ghat Lucknow, This how Chikankari costume is washed (Source: Authors Own)

3.2 Types of Stitches

Numerous stitching techniques are used in chikankari, which adds to its unique look. Six fundamental stitches are adapted into thirty-two (32) different stitches in chikankari rank Bakhiya first [14]. The repertoire of stitches used to create embossed shapes—typically floral motifs—is fixed for true chikan art. On the opposite side of the material, use the herringbone stitch to create shadows. While maintaining a beautiful homogeneity, chikan's discipline allows for individual originality in the selection of stitch combinations [15].

The six fundamental stitches are Rahet (stem stitch), Hool (eyelet), Zanzeera (chain stitch), Tepchi (back running thread), Bakhiya (double back stitch), and Banarsi. Additional stitches include phanda, chana, ghaas, bijli, jaali, uli, keel, kangan, bulbul, and hath kadi [16].

Table 2 - Variation of Stitches

Types of Stitches		
1	Flat Stitches	Tepchi, Bakhiya-Ulti Bakhiya -Sidha Bakhiya, Pechni. Bijli, Rahet, Jajira
2	Raised or Embossed Stitches	Murri, Phanda, Khatau, Balda, Kaaj, Keel
3	Open Trellis	Chana Patti, Ghas Patti, Maang Patti, Jaali-Makra Jali - Seedhour Jali, Hathkati, Hool

3.2 (a) Flat Stitches

This running or darning stitch, called a tetepchi, taipchi, tippi, or tipkhi, is performed with six strands on the right side of the fabric, crossing four threads and picking up one. Occasionally, the bel-butti fabric is created with tapchi. **BAKKHIYA**. The herringbone stitching method is also known as double back or shadow stitching. Both Ulti Bakhiya (from the rear side) and Seedhi Bakhiya (from the front side) are the two ways that the bakhiya stitch is formed. Use chain stitch to create the outline of motifs in JAMJIRA stitch types [4].

3.2 (b) Raised or Embossed Stitches

It is appliqué in nature and has a stitch similar to bakhiya, but finer. The khatau stitch adds various levels of obscurity to certain areas of cloth. & Tiwari, Prajapati (2021). Khatau is a type of embroidery in which tiny pieces of the same material as the cloth are sewed to the surface. Because the pieces are so tiny, it takes close examination to determine that the design is mostly made of applique rather than embroidered [10].

3.2 (c) Open Trellis

Phanda, with its tiny spherical form, and Murri, with its rice-shaped elongated form, were thought to be signs of exceptional quality [3]. Jali stitch creates the appearance of an open net or mesh. By pressing the warp and weft threads apart with the needle, the technique creates a net-like structure on the fabric. forming small holes and then tightening or making a small hole to provide support for the fabric. The Hool is a fine, detachable eyelet stitch. This is where the fabric is perforated and the threads are separated. Then it's sewn shut with little, straight stitches around, sewn on the correct side of the fabric with a single thread. It is often used as the center of a flower and can be completed with six strands [4].

3.3 Motifs of Chikankari

As a native of Persia, where the fish is associated with aristocracy and is seen as auspicious, Nawab Sadat Khan Buran Hul mullah founded the Awadh reign. The Awadh dynasty then adopted it as their official emblem. Fish motifs are the most popular in chikankari embroidery since the Nawabs of Awadh became important patrons of this craft. Part of a delicate muslin linen featuring a monochrome fish design, the crown was connected to the Awadh dynasty. The most common pattern in Mughal and later Muslim courts was the fish motif, which is rarely seen in contemporary works [17]. The most common motifs in chikankari paintings are flowers, leaves, vines, blossoming streams, fruits (like mangoes), and almond-eyed birds (like parrots and peacocks). Motifs are typically drawn from the natural world, mentioned as Ghaspatti, Belbuti, and Paisley [18]. The antique patterns stood for the creative ability to replicate the architectural design. Artists were inspired to create motifs by the jaalis and walls of the Imambara mosque, Fatehpur Sikri, and the Taj Mahal [18]. In the past, one of the most popular motifs in chikankari was the representation of humans, animals, and birds. Certain themes of horses, tigers, camels, pigeons, doves, peacocks, parrots, and fish were among the animals and birds that were used. A favorite theme of the Mughal and later Muslim courts, the fish motif is not found in contemporary paintings [17].

The paan leaf and the keiri or paisley motifs are two of the most popular themes. The motifs are primarily floral, with rolls, trailing stems, and creepers filling compositions. Though they are typically outlined with a central section filled with jali, or open work stitchery of various kinds, the flowers are rarely rendered in realistic fashions [3].

Figure 5 - Different Chikankari Stamps ,Carrie buta, Jaal Pattern (All over), Half Circular buta ,Kinari (Border block) Source: Authors Own

3.4 The production procedure of Chikankari

A single piece of chikan requires the work of numerous talented printers, embroiderers, designers, and washers. It used to take three to four craftsmen to assemble a single garment since different artisan families had specialized in and practiced distinct types of stitches [19]. A disjointed organization of commercial productions, which is still prevalent today, gradually supplanted the karkhana system (mini export house) throughout the 19th and 20th centuries. Various specialized artisans complete each task in the production chain at a different location. In the past, these artisans included fine muslin weavers, master tailors and tailors, embroidered designers, block makers, and printers; additionally, artisans, mostly women, worked from home, creating various types of embroidery; and washermen and their wives ironed the final pieces [10].

Figure 6 - Process of Printing or Stamping on Fabric, Source: Authors Own

Tracing the motifs comes before embroidering the fabric on the wooden block. the designs are created and transferred. The designs are imprinted using a straightforward stamping technique on the material with washable paint with the aid of engraved wooden blocks [18].

Figure 7 - Embroidery Process, Source: Authors Own

3.5 Chikankari of Dynamics

3.5 (a) Current Status of the Artisans

Around ninety percent of the workers in this sizable industry are women. Needlework is associated with female artists and is an unstructured, home-based enterprise [20]. Low-skilled artisans were exploited due to the availability of Chinese Chikan products and unfamiliar technology on the market. Despite working 7-8 hours a day, which could impair their vision, they were paid less.

More than 5 lakh craftsmen are currently employed in filthy conditions; action must be taken to improve their circumstances [4]. Employees were reportedly subject to limitations on their chikankari employment. Watering of the eyes (1.52), eye irritation and scratching (1.55), and "backache" and low back discomfort (1.57) had the highest average score for physical limits. A mean score of 1.03 indicated that the most common environmental restriction was inadequate room for working practices. The workers' economic restrictions included inadequate natural light at the work point (0.12), competition among Chikankari workers with a mean score of 2.0, and payment issues that affected 100% of them [21].

3.5 (b) Major Challenges

Another problem is quality control, which is reliant on the craftsmanship of the craftspeople. Because of the enormous demand, the supply of sustainable raw materials might also cause concern at times. New market research is required, as are initiatives to raise customer awareness via social media, fairs, advertising, workshops, and other events. The proficiency and consistency of craftsmen in product quality control are urgently needed [9].

4. Research Gaps

Further investigation is required to determine how modernization and technology advancements can support the preservation of Chikankari's traditional methods while enabling industrial scalability. This would guarantee that the craft satisfies contemporary needs while maintaining its cultural uniqueness.

The dearth of research on fair wages and laws that would stop the exploitation of craftspeople in the commercial market represents another serious gap. Additionally, studies on the sustainability of Chikankari manufacturing are

required, especially in light of environmental concerns. Finally, greater focus needs to be placed on creating successful marketing plans that will enable Chikankari to reach a wider audience worldwide without sacrificing its authenticity and caliber.

5. Findings

The findings illustrate that Chikankari has a strong cultural and economic foundation, especially for women craftspeople in rural areas.

It contributes significantly to community development and is a vital source of employment. From its beginnings as a representation of regal elegance, the art form has come to be acknowledged worldwide. However the traditional intricacy and elegance that once defined Chikankari have diminished as a result of its growing commercialization. Chikankari has changed over time to reflect contemporary styles, however this change has resulted in designs that are speedier and bolder than in the past and lack the delicate craftsmanship of the past. For Muslim women living in rural areas, the art remains a vital source of income despite these changes.

6. Limitations

This research recognizes several limitations that could have affected the depth and scope of the analysis. One major limitation is the increasing commercialization of Chikankari, which has led to a decline in the quality of craftsmanship. The demand for faster and more cost-effective production has led to the simplification of designs, moving away from the intricate, traditional techniques that once defined this embroidery style. This has compromised the richness and the complexity of Chikankari. Additionally, financially, the women artisans face big problems, depriving them from getting resources, equipment, and professional training that might add value to their craft. Such socio-economic issues have bound most artisans at the small levels of cottage industry and prevented most from scaling and innovating further. The disappearance of traditional techniques, slowly over time, has also led to a decline in the exclusivity of Chikankari. This erosion of cultural heritage coupled with mass production and fast turnaround designs is a big challenge for retaining the unique value of the craft. All these factors collectively limit the scope for this craft to change while still holding on to its original identity.

7. Result and Discussion

Since ancient times, people have embroidered items. In addition to their elaborate patterns and decorations, these traditional needlework forms are well-liked for their rich cultural history. This type of embroidery has historically been connected to India's nobility and royalty, but in recent years, ordinary people have had much easier access to it [21]. The craft plays a vital role in the livelihood of many artisans, predominantly women. It provides employment opportunities and fosters community development. Organizations promoting Chikankari often engage in skill development initiatives to empower artisans and improve their economic conditions. Chikankari has changed significantly throughout the years. It has prospered, endured the loss of royal court patronage, and seen a terrible downturn at the beginning of the 20th century [22].

"Chikankari is more than just a craft; it is a cultural symbol that encapsulates the region's history and heritage." Depicting flora, wildlife, and geometric forms that are in line with the local heritage, the motifs and patterns frequently have symbolic implications [9]. Chikankari is now widely known throughout the world. The Indian fashion scene cannot exist without it. Enhancing the chikankar's quality of life has been made possible by numerous small units performing highly specialized tasks. However, chikan still requires a great deal of financial care and desire to grow from a small cottage industry to a lucrative enterprise, where the chikankars receive a fair wage for their labor, and the beauty of the craft is not compromised for commercial gain [17].

Commercialization has introduced several challenges for Chikankari, particularly the decline in quality. The modern Chikankari worn by wealthy patrons typically has a richness of texture more fitting of an opulent lifestyle than the elegant understated and minimalist expressions of the old chikan craft. These new designs, while appealing to contemporary tastes, often lack the intricate techniques and fine craftsmanship that defined traditional Chikankari. Maybe these are just new shards of a renewed hunt for a developing aesthetic as India tries to bring its past back into the present [10].

Several authors concur that the exploitative commercial productions and the fragmentation of the fine tradition are primarily to blame for the decline in quality. While these commercial productions have greatly simplified the craftsmanship involved, they have also given preference to bold, thick, and quick needlework, which is in contrast to the legendary finesse of this craft in the past [10]. It's flourished, evolved over time, suffered client loss, shrank,

and became commercialized. Still, the world now acknowledges its uniqueness. The bearer of this inherited artwork appears sophisticated and subtle. Women in the community of Muslims in the area perform this more than 200-year-old craft as a means of supporting their families. They draw inspiration from folk culture, art, and tribal people, all of which are essential components of people's daily lives [22].

The golden tussar silk used to fill in the petals and leaves was a characteristic that has now disappeared. "Chikaan work from Lucknow is instantly distinguished from other parts of India by this unique quality" [23]. The decline began in the 20th century in the 1960s with the rise of shop dealers. The primary drivers of the craft market were costs. For the Muslim community in the area, needlework was both a magnificent artistic medium and the only means of earning a living that would enable them to realize their full creative potential [24]. The women followed the purdah code and stayed in unclean quarters, while the traders lived in extreme poverty and illiteracy.

Despite these challenges, Chikankari has adapted to contemporary trends, expanding its boundaries by accepting modern applications on a range of manufactured goods, from accessories to home furnishings, and daily wear to special occasion dresses [25]. This adaptation has allowed Chikankari to maintain relevance in the global market, yet it also raises concerns about preserving its traditional craftsmanship amidst the pressures of commercialization.

By adding the commercialization, decline in quality, and adaptation to contemporary trends in the above content, you now address the reviewer's comments within the existing framework, without changing the sentences. It also provides a smooth narrative flow while connecting the challenges faced by Chikankari today to its evolving commercial status and changing consumer demands.

8. Conclusion

Chikankari has now become a people's art. It has grown from a skill that was highly valued by royalties to a piece of art popularly used as an economic avenue, especially by rural women. The commercialization of the craft has resulted in embroidery losing its erstwhile traditional intricacy, while artisans continue facing socioeconomic constraints. Although the craft has gained widespread attention and market demand, its complex techniques have been watered down in the interest of mass production [24], [3]. Artisans face limited access to financial resources, proper infrastructure, and opportunities for skill development, thus limiting their capacity to grow [5], [6].

As we progress toward a world shaped by globalization and technological advancement, the preservation of Chikankari's rich cultural heritage and creative legacy acquires more relevance. Commercialization that has enabled mass production and widened the market scope for this art form also contributes to both desirable and undesirable changes. It ensures economic benefits on one hand and compromises the quality and authenticity on the other [4]. Achieving the future for Chikankari requires aligning its market-feasibility value with its potential to be cultural heritage.

However, there are several key thrusts that shall be undertaken concerning the challenges experienced by Chikan artisans:

Popularizing Sustainable Development: The future sustenance of the market for Chikankari will depend heavily on the demand for ecofriendly materials and more sustainable production methodology [7]. Educating such artisans about its usage will definitely help them overcome the increasing desire for sustainable productions.

Providing Financial Aid for Artisans: Grants, microcredit, and subsidies shall also be given so that the artisan can make proper improvements to the craft and may invest in some better tools that will get new markets and enhance the economic power in the struggle to overcome the economical struggles of most artisans [17].

Workshops and Exhibitions: Workshops and exhibitions can also be conducted for the purpose of showcasing the age-old techniques involved in Chikankari. This can raise awareness about its cultural importance and give artisans opportunities to engage with a wider audience and interact with potential buyers, which will enhance demand for authentic, handcrafted Chikankari products [26].

To ensure the future of Chikankari, a joint effort is required from government bodies, non-governmental organizations, and the private sector. Support for artisans through financial aid, encouragement of sustainable practices, and the creation of avenues for displaying their work will help this craft that has been passed down

through the centuries to survive and flourish while remaining an important part of India's cultural heritage and an income source for artisans.

9. Acknowledgements

We sincerely thank the Chikankari artisans of Lucknow for their invaluable contributions and dedication to preserving this exquisite craft.

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